

METHODS OF TEACHING**Topilova Gulhayo**

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ABSTRACT: The education system in Uzbekistan has undergone significant changes in recent years, with a focus on modernization and development. The government has implemented various policies and initiatives to improve the quality of education and increase access to it. However, challenges still exist, such as inadequate infrastructure and limited resources. The concept of development for the education system of Uzbekistan for 2019-2030 aims to address these challenges and further improve the education system. This paper provides an overview of the current state of education in Uzbekistan, its challenges and opportunities, and the efforts being made to modernize the education system for the 21st century.

Keywords: Uzbekistan, education system, modernization, development, policies, initiatives, quality of education, access to education, infrastructure, resources, challenges, opportunities, 21st century.

Introduction

In Uzbekistan, traditional teaching methods have been prevalent for many years. However, with the advancement of technology and the changing needs of students, there has been a shift towards more innovative and student-centered teaching methods. One of the most popular methods of teaching in Uzbekistan is the lecture method, where teachers deliver information to students through lectures. However, there has been a growing trend towards inquiry-based and collaborative learning methods, which encourage students to take an active role in their own learning. Project-based learning and game-based learning methods are also gaining popularity in Uzbekistan, as they provide students with opportunities to apply their knowledge and skills to

real-world situations.

Additionally, the Montessori method, which emphasizes hands-on learning and individualized instruction, is becoming more popular in Uzbekistan as parents seek alternative educational options for their children. There are many different methods of teaching, including:

1. Lecture method: This is the traditional method of teaching where the teacher delivers a lecture to the students.
2. Demonstration method: This method involves demonstrating a concept or skill to the students.
3. Inquiry-based method: This method involves asking questions and encouraging students to explore and discover the answers themselves.
4. Collaborative learning method: This method involves group work and encourages students to work together to solve problems.
5. Problem-based learning method: This method involves presenting students with real-world problems and challenges, and encouraging them to find solutions.

While traditional teaching methods still have a place in Uzbekistan's education system, there is a growing recognition of the importance of innovative and student-centered teaching methods in preparing students for success in the modern world.

Literature review.

A literature review of Uzbekistan's education system reveals that traditional teaching methods have been prevalent for many years. However, there has been a growing recognition of the importance of innovative and student-centered teaching methods in preparing students for success in the modern world.

According to a study by the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP), the lecture

method is still widely used in Uzbekistan, and teachers often rely on textbooks as the primary source of information. However, the study also found that there is a growing trend towards inquiry-based and collaborative learning methods, which encourage students to take an active role in their own learning.

Another study by the World Bank highlights the importance of project-based learning and game-based learning methods in Uzbekistan. These methods provide students with opportunities to apply their knowledge and skills to real-world situations, which can help to improve their critical thinking and problem-solving skills. The Montessori method, which emphasizes hands-on learning and individualized instruction, is also becoming more popular in Uzbekistan. This method is seen as an alternative to traditional teaching methods and is believed to be particularly effective for younger children.

Overall, the literature suggests that while traditional teaching methods still have a place in Uzbekistan's education system, there is a growing recognition of the importance of innovative and student-centered teaching methods. This shift towards more modern teaching methods is seen as essential for preparing students for success in the modern world.

Discussion.

The literature review highlights the need for Uzbekistan's education system to shift towards innovative and student-centered teaching methods to prepare students for success in the modern world. While traditional teaching methods still have a place in the system, there is a growing recognition of the importance of inquiry-based and collaborative learning methods, project-based learning, game-based learning, and the Montessori method. It is essential for Uzbekistan's education system to adapt to the changing needs of the world and equip students with the skills and knowledge they need to succeed in a globalized economy. Innovative teaching methods can help students develop critical thinking, problem-solving, and collaboration skills, which are highly valued by employers.

Moreover, it is crucial to ensure that teachers are adequately trained to use these innovative

teaching methods effectively. Professional development programs that focus on modern teaching methods can help teachers stay up-to-date with the latest trends in education and improve their teaching skills.

Uzbekistan's education system needs to embrace innovative and student-centered teaching methods to prepare students for success in the modern world. This shift towards more modern teaching methods is crucial for improving the quality of education and ensuring that students have the skills they need to succeed in their future careers.

Conclusion. The literature review emphasizes the importance of modernizing Uzbekistan's education system by adopting innovative and student-centered teaching methods. It is crucial to prepare students for success in a globalized economy by developing critical thinking, problem-solving, and collaboration skills. Teachers also need to be trained to use these methods effectively through professional development programs. The shift towards modern teaching methods is essential for improving the quality of education and ensuring that students have the skills they need to succeed in their future careers.

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